

Intellectual Adjustment as Correlates of Academic Performance among Public Senior School Students in North Central Nigeria

Friday Maha¹ and Auta Rosemary Ezra²

¹Department of Educational Foundation, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

²Department of Educational Foundation, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study assessed intellectual adjustment as correlates of academic performance among public senior school students in north central Nigeria. Three structured questionnaires, namely, Psychosocial Adjustment Questionnaire (PAQ), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) were used for data collection. These questionnaires were administered to 383 students drawn from 16 schools across North-Central States of Nigeria. The collected data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation to answer research question on the basis of the values of r (coefficient of correlation). For correlation coefficient value below 0.50, it was considered low while any above 0.50 was considered high. On the other hand, the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significance level by comparing the p -value (probability values) of Pearson's product moment correlation obtained from SPSS application with the significance level at 0.05. Results reveal that there is significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in north central Nigeria. The study therefore, recommended among others that orientations should be organized for students and workshops/seminars for teachers.

Keywords: Intellectual adjustment, Academic performance, Students, Public, Senior secondary, School.

Correspondence to: Auta Rosemary Ezra, e-mail: ezrarosemary@gmail.com

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Introduction

The transition from high school to tertiary institution is a major life change for many young people. This progression usually comes with new responsibilities and challenges. When students graduate from primary and are admitted into secondary schools, the students usually face unfamiliar experiences as well as a more demanding social and academic environment. Intellectual adjustment can therefore refer to as students' adoption and adaption to changes in their attitudes, behaviours, values, rules, regulations and social norms of the school environment in order to fit into and be accepted into new study environment. It is an individual's ability to meet academic demands, to be attentive, to participate in class activities and become a learner capable of independent learning. Researches show that students' inability to adjust to the school psychosocial environment is one of the major causes of withdrawal from school, as well as academic frustration. Wang et al (2016) affirmed that intellectual adjustment entails dealing with various scholarly demands, while sustaining the drive to engage in other goal-oriented tasks. Similarly, Baker and Siryk (1999) viewed that intellectual adjustment is multifaceted and involves an array of demands varying in kinds and degrees which require a variety of coping responses. In schools, students have the opportunity to join an academic club. These clubs within the school includes fellow classmates, other classes, and staff. During class, students are expected to engage in intellectual discussions with their faculty, raise questions and, at times, even challenge them. In turn, students will be exposed to new ideas and subject areas and career choices that they may have never considered before.

Moreover, students have many obstacles to overcome in order to attain academic excellence. It takes a lot more than just studying to achieve a successful school career. These students undertake a journey full of varying experiences of course. Not many of them regard all these experiences as exciting. Some young people see most experiences of life as unfortunate. To some, experiences of life are homely and becoming because, experience means, different things to different people; and experience that stagnates people in life is intellectual maladjustment (Wakeh and Omoegun, 2020). Intellectual adjustment problems can pose their own threat to students' academic achievement and make them conclude that nothing more can happen in their favour in life again (Ayeni, 2021). Additionally, safer school environment improves students' learning (Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain (2015). Study by Duckworth and Seligman, (2015) found a linear relationship between self-regulation and academic achievement. Adolescent whose social life is free of problem will be well adjusted. It is in line with the assertions that this study assesses intellectual adjustment as correlates of academic performance among public senior school students in north central Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study

1. What is the relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria.

Research Method

In this study, the correlation research design was used. Three questionnaires titled Psychosocial Adjustment Questionnaire (PAQ), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) were used to collect data. The PAQ, MAT and ELAT were administered to 383 students drawn from 16 schools across North-Central States of Nigeria using simple random sampling technique of lucky dip. To answer the research questions, the Pearson product moment correlation was used on the basis of the values of r (coefficient of correlation). Here, any correlation coefficient value below 0.50 was considered low while those above 0.50 was considered high. Additionally, the formulated hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significance level by comparing the p -value (probability values) of Pearson's product moment correlation obtained from SPSS application with the significance level at 0.05.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: what is relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria?

Table 1. Calculated r -values of Pearson's Product Moment on Level of Relationship between Intellectual Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Public Senior Secondary School students in North Central Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Variables	N	R	Remarks
1	Intellectual Adjustment	383	0.106	Positively weak relationship
2	Academic Achievement	383		

Table 1 shows the level of relationship between intellectual adjustment and students' academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Results show that

calculated r values are given as 0.106. This value is below the benchmark value of 0.50. Hence, there is a positively low relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Table 2. Calculated P-values of Pearson's Product Moment on the Significance of Relationship between Intellectual Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Public Senior Secondary School students in North Central Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Variables	N	R	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
1	Intellectual Adjustment	383	0.106	0.038	Reject H ₀	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	383				

Table 2 shows the significance of relationship between intellectual adjustment and students' academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Results show that calculated p-values are given as 0.038. This value is below the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the formulated hypothesis is rejected indicating there is a significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The findings from the hypothesis revealed there is a significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central States, Nigeria. Similar result was reported by Al-Hendawi, Wendy and Hussein (2022) which indicates significant relationship between school intellectual adjustment and academic achievement in Qatari secondary school students. Intellectual adjustment problems can pose their own threat to students' academic achievement and make them conclude that nothing more can happen in their favour in life again (Ayeni, 2021). Similarly, Kumari and Kamala, (2022) shows agreement with the findings that intellectual adjustment is significantly correlated with academic achievement. da Costa et al. (2021) also revealed that intellectual adjustment plays an important role in students' learning. Safer school environment improves students' learning (Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain, 2015). Study by Duckworth and Seligman, (2015) found a linear relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic achievement.

Conclusion

Intellectual adjustment as correlates of academic performance among public senior school students in north central Nigeria is presented. Results of the study show that there is a significant relationship between intellectual adjustment and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in north central Nigeria. The study therefore, recommended among others that orientations should be organized for students and workshops/seminars for teachers. Furthermore, schools should ensure that learners receive orientation on periodic basis in order to sensitize them on how they can intellectually adjust in school to enhance their academic achievement while Ministries of Education within North Central Zone should organize workshops/seminars to educate teachers on how they can help students adjust intellectually in school for the purpose of improving their grades.

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